

Biocompatibility and Long-Term Stability of DNA-Based Organic Mixed Conductors for Bioelectronics

Sarka Hradilova, Katharina Matura, Munise Cobet, Ariana Opletalova, Yolanda Salinas, Niyazi Serdar Sariciftci, Serpil Tekoglu,* and Katerina Polakova*

In the field of bioelectronics, designing novel organic mixed ionic-electronic conductors (OMIECs) is crucial to overcome the limitations in terms of biocompatibility and long-term stability. Polymeric OMIECs are reported for their potential applications in implantable devices to record and stimulate biological signals. Deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) templated PEDOT and polypyrrole are synthesized via oxidative chemical polymerization. The biocompatibility and long-term chemical stability of conductive composites PEDOT:DNA and PPy:DNA are evaluated and compared to PEDOT:PSS. To examine *in vitro* cytotoxicity, NIH 3T3 cells are cultured on thin-films of PEDOT:PSS and DNA-based biocomposites. The visual determination of cell morphology and adhesion are carried out by fluorescent optical microscopy and atomic force microscopy (AFM) imaging. The acute and long-term cell viability is performed by using flow cytometry. After 96 h of incubation, the cells maintain over 80% viability, retaining their morphology and adhesion properties similar to control cells on plastic or glass samples. This indicates that all tested samples demonstrate high biocompatibility. The material stability of PEDOT:DNA and PPy:DNA is investigated by integrating the materials into organic electrochemical transistors (OECTs). The results confirm an efficient ion-to-electron transduction in OECTs and long-term chemical stability after storing the materials for up to 5 years.

conduction mechanism. Owing to their functionalities for bioelectronics, mixed conductors can provide an excellent platform for cell growth and recording cell activities.^[6] These bioelectronic platforms can be used for monitoring and stimulating cellular functions.^[3,7–9]

PEDOT:PSS is the most widely studied OMIEC, which can be regarded as a composite material comprising a conductive polymer PEDOT doped by a negatively charged polymer electrolyte, polystyrene sulfonate (PSS).^[5] PEDOT:PSS is a prominent conductive polymer for being highly conductive, commercially available, solution processable, chemically and mechanically stable.^[10] However, the biocompatibility of PSS within the composite is under debate in the field considering its acidity for long-term applications.^[11] Several reports have attributed that cell adhesion can be restricted by acidity/toxicity of PSS stabilizer.^[12–16] There are few studies that proves the long-term stability of PEDOT:PSS.^[17,18] Malliaras et al. showed the adequate *in vitro* stability of PEDOT:PSS on microelectrode arrays for up to 3–4 months.^[18]

To bridge the gap between electronics and biology to improve biocompatibility and biointegration strategies, tremendous efforts have been spent through material modifications, composite formation, and post-treatment techniques.^[17,19,20] One of

1. Introduction

Organic mixed ionic-electronic conductors (OMIECs) are a promising class of materials for designing and constructing devices in the field of bioelectronics by coupling the electron and ion transport at the interface of biology.^[1–5] OMIECs can efficiently facilitate ion-to-electron transduction by offering a dual

S. Hradilova, M. Cobet, A. Opletalova, K. Polakova
Czech Advanced Technology and Research Institute (CATRIN)
Regional Centre of Advanced Technologies and Materials (RCPTM)
Palacký University Olomouc
Šlechtitelů 27, Olomouc 779 00, Czech Republic
E-mail: katerina.polakova@upol.cz

K. Matura, N. S. Sariciftci, S. Tekoglu
Linz Institute for Solar Cells (LIOS) and Institute of Physical Chemistry
Johannes Kepler University Linz
Altenbergerstrasse 69, Linz A-4040, Austria
E-mail: serpil.tekoglu@jku.at
Y. Salinas
Institute of Polymer Chemistry
Johannes Kepler University Linz
Altenbergerstrasse 69, Linz A-4040, Austria
Y. Salinas
Institute of Applied Chemistry
IMC Krems University of Applied Sciences
Piaristengasse 1, Krems A-3500, Austria

 The ORCID identification number(s) for the author(s) of this article can be found under <https://doi.org/10.1002/admi.202500412>

© 2025 The Author(s). Advanced Materials Interfaces published by Wiley-VCH GmbH. This is an open access article under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution](#) License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

DOI: 10.1002/admi.202500412

the strategies is the removal of insulating PSS via acid treatment to enhance the crystallinity of the PEDOT:PSS assemblies, yet, the residual PSS within nanoparticles cannot be completely eliminated.^[20] Minimized PSS residues in the crystalized film have substantially improved the operational stability of electrochemical transistors.^[17]

In another approach, biopolymers have been implemented as a counterion during the synthesis of various conductive polymers such as PEDOT, polypyrrole (PPy), and polyaniline (PANI).^[21–26] In our recent work, we have utilized sulfated nanocellulose crystals as counterion nano-template for PEDOT, resulting high transconductance values in organic electrochemical transistors (OECTs).^[25] In another study, the biocompatibility of PEDOT:bacterial cellulose dropped after adding PSS into the composite to improve the conduction.^[27] Toxicity evolution of PEDOT:biopolymer in vitro using L929 fibroblast cells as well as in vivo studies have shown non-toxicity.^[28] The results confirm that this class of composites can be promising electrode interface material for neural recordings. Among other PEDOT:biopolymer composites, PEDOT stabilized with deoxyribonucleic acid as a counterion (PEDOT:DNA) exhibits higher ionic conductivity with respect to PEDOT:PSS.^[29] As pioneering work, DNA has been reported for organic field-effect transistors (OFETs) by our group.^[30,31] DNA-based solid polymer electrolytes and DNA-based polymers have been investigated for electroluminescent devices and OFETs, respectively.^[32,33] However, the field-effect transistor has shown a resistance-like behavior due to the thick (1 μm) and non-uniform polymer layer.^[33] We have recently developed two biocomposites comprising DNA as a dopant for PEDOT and PPy to integrate as a channel material in OECTs.^[24] This preliminary study demonstrated the applicability of proposed materials in OECTs as a proof-of-concept for the first time. However, a comprehensive study for understanding the material-cell interaction and determining long-term stability requires a long period of time in order to repeat the experimental procedure. Therefore, we have conducted research over an extended period to observe the long-term stability and biocompatibility of these materials as an important follow-up study showing their applicability in biomedicine.

In this study, the in vitro biocompatibility and long-term chemical stability of designed biocomposites PEDOT:DNA and PPy:DNA were investigated thoroughly. For in vitro cytotoxicity experiments, NIH 3T3 mouse fibroblast cell line was used for incubation and proliferation on the thin films of DNA-based biocomposites and PEDOT:PSS as reference material. For a visual determination of cell morphology and adhesion as well as the viability of these cells, fluorescent optical microscopy was engaged by using a Calcein-AM green fluorescent dye stain. The effect of direct contact of cells on the samples and cell adhesion ability was further evaluated via atomic force microscopy (AFM) imaging. The viability experiments were carried out using the flow cytometry technique. The DNA-based conductive polymer composites showed high biocompatibility established from flow cytometry even after 96 h of incubation. For the long-term stability predictions, the chemical stability of the materials was analyzed by using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and Raman spectroscopy. The particle size and polydispersity were evaluated by using dynamic light scattering method (DLS). The morphology of biocomposite thin-films was investigated via scanning electron

microscopy (SEM). As a final step, the stability of PEDOT:DNA and PPy:DNA was examined in organic electrochemical transistors (OECTs) after storing the materials at 4 °C for up to 5 years. The device results confirmed an efficient ion-to-electron transduction in OECTs and the shelf-life stability of both biocomposites.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Biocompatibility

The cytotoxicity tests were carried out for the designed biocomposites PEDOT:DNA and PPy:DNA (**Figure 1**) as well as reference material PEDOT:PSS after adding the specific surfactants and cross-linker. DBSA (4-dodecylbenzenesulfonic acid), glycerol, and the cross-linker (GOPS: 3-glycidyoxypropyl)trimethoxysilane) have been commonly employed to deposit channel materials in OECTs against delamination of the channel polymer during measurement.^[34] The thin-films of each composite material were coated on glass slides using their respective dispersions of 94.5% (v/v) mixed with 0.5% (v/v) DBSA, 5% (v/v) glycerol, and subsequently 1% (v/v) GOPS vs 100% total solution volume to provide a platform for cell growth.

One of the important parameters depicting normal physiological functions of the cells is the changes in cell morphology and cell adhesion. For a visual determination of cell morphology and adhesion as well as the viability of these cells, Calcein-AM green fluorescent dye was used to detect live cells under optical microscopy in a fluorescence mode. **Figure 2** represents the micrographs of NIH 3T3 fibroblast cells obtained from an optical fluorescent microscope after 24 h of incubation on control glass, PEDOT:PSS, PEDOT:DNA, and PPy:DNA thin-film surfaces.

Green fluorescence from Calcein in cytosol confirms that all tested samples contain only live cells, as no red signal was observed from Propidium Iodide (PI) that indicates dead cells. No significant differences were noted in cell morphology or adhesion capability between the control group (**Figure 2a**) and the cells cultured on the tested biocomposite samples (**Figure 2c,d**). As depicted in (**Figure S1**, Supporting Information), the preliminary cell study of pristine PEDOT:PSS (without additives) delaminated from the glass slide within the first 24 h of the experiment as reported elsewhere previously.^[16,35] This shows the significant effect of the cross-linker (GOPS) against delamination for all samples in **Figure 2a–d**, not only during 24 h incubation period but also the whole experimental process for 96 h.

In addition to optical microscopy studies, the effect of direct contact of cells with the samples on glass support for their cell adhesion ability was also evaluated via atomic force microscopy (AFM) imaging. **Figure 3** represents AFM images of fixed NIH 3T3 cells acquired with a scan size of 100 × 100 μm for all samples. High-resolution height (left) and respective 3D (right) images of living cells show the substructures of cell membrane adhered to the glass control as well as on the thin-films of PEDOT:PSS, PEDOT:DNA, and PPy:DNA. The nuclei region i) and the cell border ii) can be clearly distinguished on the topography of the cell surface (fixed) in **Figure 3c,d**. The obtained topography images were converted in a 3D format, and the images were presented quantitatively in lateral (x and y) and height (z) directions.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of synthetic route and DNA:conductive polymer biocomposites (left) as final product. The chemical structures of DNA (as dopant) as well as PEDOT and polypyrrole are represented (right). *This illustrative material from wikimedia commons licensed CC BY-SA 4.0 Dr. Thomas Spletstoesser. Reprinted with permission.

The maxima of height profile for each substrate was slightly altered at the range of 44–60 μm with respect to cell height and surface roughness. The respective phase contrast images of the samples and the AFM top-view camera images are depicted as supporting data in Figures S2 and S3 (Supporting Information). The topographical images of fixed fibroblast cells reveal that the

cells adhered to the film surface as a favorable place to grow and proliferate.

LIVE/DEAD viability assay was evaluated using flow cytometry. Flow cytometry is a fast, high-throughput, and highly accurate technique that provides information about each individual cell in the whole population with statistics.^[36–38] The fluorescence-based

Figure 2. Optical fluorescent microscope images of NIH 3T3 cells after 24 h of incubation on A) the control glass, B) PEDOT:PSS, C) PEDOT:DNA, and D) PPy:DNA thin-film surfaces; green fluorescence is showing alive cells due to the Calcein dye. Scale bars = 200 μm .

Figure 3. AFM images of fixed *NIH 3T3* cells were acquired with a scan size of $100 \times 100 \mu\text{m}$ for all samples. High-resolution 2D and 3D height images of living cells recorded in low force contact mode. The images show the substructures of cell membrane adhered on A) the glass control, B) PEDOT:PSS, C) PEDOT:DNA, and D) PPy:DNA. Scale bars = $20 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 4. The viability of cells growing on the various substrates (control plastics, glass, PEDOT:DNA, PPy:DNA, and PEDOT:PSS) after 24, 48, and 96 h was evaluated by flow cytometry via LIVE/DEAD viability/cytotoxicity assay. Notice: positive controls were cells after heating (60 °C). Three independent experiments were performed and mean and standard deviation \pm (SD) were calculated.

LIVE/DEAD assay reduced the risk of the possible interference of dark (PPy) samples in comparison to absorbance-based measurements.

We used a commercial LIVE/DEAD kit containing two fluorescence probes PI and Calcein-AM to distinguish between the populations of dead and live cells. PI is able to intercalate into the DNA of dead cells with a ruptured cell membrane, while live cells dispose active esterases that catalyze the non-fluorescent Calcein-AM to highly fluorescent Calcein. As shown in **Figure 4** direct contact between *NIH 3T3* cells and the tested materials did not lead to a significant decrease in cell viability compared to control cells grown in a plastic chamber or glass alone. Viability in all samples is above 80%, indicating that the tested materials are biocompatible.^[39] Interestingly, the number of viable cells increased over time across all samples, suggesting that the cells are being adapted to the surface characteristics of the substrates during the incubation period. Only in the case of PPy:DNA sample, after 96 h, the cell viability slightly decreased from 96% to 84%. The reduction in viable cells can be attributed to unreacted monomer units remaining in the composite. Cheng et al. reported a similar trend with the relatively lower biocompatibility with the increase of conductive polymer components in the biocomposite (without PSS).^[40] The authors hypothesized that unreacted monomer residues in the composite might create a detrimental effect on cell activity.

In this study, we demonstrate high biocompatibility of PEDOT:PSS, with a cell viability of 97% after 96 h of cell culture. These results were obtained using flow cytometry, which enables single-cell analysis and provides a more accurate assessment of

cytotoxicity. Our findings are notably more favorable than previously reported values obtained using other assay methods, as summarized in Table S1 (Supporting Information). For instance, Tumová et al. reported a relative cell viability of $\approx 40\%$ for mouse 3T3 fibroblast cells after 48 h of incubation with PEDOT:PSS, using the MTT assay.^[16] In their study, the glass control yielded $\approx 70\%$ cell viability, indicating a notable decrease that may be attributed to the assay method used. Similarly, Dominguez-Alfaro et al. used the Bradford assay and reported $\approx 43\%$ cell viability for PEDOT:PSS after 24 h of incubation with *NIH 3T3* fibroblast cells.^[41] In comparison, our flow cytometry-based results show a viability of $\approx 94\%$ for PEDOT:PSS after 48 h, relative to 97% for the glass control. Higher cell viability values ($>80\%$) for PEDOT:PSS have been only achieved through treatments such as cross-linking, incorporation of ionic liquids and ethylene glycol, or post-processing methods like laser treatment and thermal annealing, aimed at enhancing biocompatibility for the on-demand fabrication of bioelectronic devices.^[42–44]

The discrepancies between our results and those from the literature may be attributed to the limitations and potential inaccuracies of bulk assays such as MTT and Bradford, which can be influenced by metabolic state, assay interference, and population heterogeneity.^[45] In contrast, flow cytometry provides direct, quantitative data at the single-cell level, reducing variability and enhancing reliability.^[36–38] In our study, by utilizing in vitro flow cytometry assay, we observed no cytotoxic response for PEDOT:PSS after 96-h incubation period. On the other hand, DNA-polymer conjugates and hydrogels are attractive for biomedical engineering applications such as biosensing, drug delivery,

tissue engineering, and cell culture.^[46] Although DNA is inherently biocompatible and readily recognized by the human body, the inclusion of synthetic polymers in hybrid DNA hydrogels may still compromise their overall biocompatibility (Table S1, Supporting Information).^[47] Importantly, no cytotoxic response was observed for the DNA-based composites in this study over the full 96-h incubation period, confirming its suitability for prolonged cell culture and potential bioelectronic applications.

In the present work, we investigated PEDOT:PSS as only one reference material. The thin-films of pristine PEDOT and polypyrrole samples could not be used as control samples for toxicity tests. The solubility and processability are the general issues for the first generation (conventional) conducting polymers such as polyacetylene, polyaniline, polypyrrole, and polythiophene.^[48] The solubility issue of PEDOT was successfully overcome by introducing polysulfonates (PSS) into the PEDOT matrix.^[5,10] Polypyrrole (earlier called as pyrrole black) is insoluble in water or organic solvents and shows limited conductivity in the range of 10^{-10} to 10^{-11} s cm⁻¹,^[49] despite its excellent biocompatibility.^[50] We could only deposit polypyrrole film as a thick, rough layer via drop-casting due to the above-mentioned restrictions. The conducting polymer morphology and thin-film thickness play an essential role while performing toxicity and cell viability tests. The optical/fluorescence microscopy technique was limited due to possible interference of these dark films. Therefore, we focused primarily on the PPy:DNA composite from practical point of view for future bioelectronics where DNA is implemented as a counterion in both polymer composites to enhance their processability as well as biocompatibility.

2.2. Long-Term Stability

The water dispersions of biocomposites were prepared and stored at $4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2$ degrees in ambient conditions with an indoor humidity level of $\approx 60\%$ for up to 5 years to monitor their long-term storage stability. The dispersions of PEDOT:DNA (March, 2019) and PPy:DNA (March, 2021) after the recorded shelf-life, were used to fabricate the electrochemical transistors. Prior to device fabrication, the chemical stability of the materials was analyzed by using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and Raman spectroscopy. The XPS survey (Figure S4, Supporting Information) confirmed the phosphorus (P) element alongside the carbon (C), oxygen (O), nitrogen (N), and sulfur (S) atoms in the biocomposites. The XPS spectra of P2p peaks (in Figure S4b,d, Supporting Information) are located at $\approx 132\text{--}133$ eV, which can be ascribed to the characteristic phosphate group (PO_4^{3-}) of DNA.^[51,52] The results confirmed the successful incorporation of the P atoms in PEDOT:DNA and PPy:DNA. This indicates that PO_4^{3-} group acts as the counter anion in DNA-based biocomposites.^[52] A complete elemental analysis with the calculated ratios of C, O, N, S, and P can be found as supporting data in Tables S2 and S3 (Supporting Information). We did not observe any residual iron ions from the oxidant after the polymerization of EDOT and pyrrole. In addition to XPS analysis, the recently obtained Raman spectrum of PEDOT:DNA (in Figure S5, Supporting Information) exhibits almost identical Raman shifts to our previous findings.^[24] The data confirms the long-term chem-

ical stability over an extended period without significant material degradation under specific storage conditions.

The particle size distribution and zeta potential distribution of the biocomposites, PEDOT:PSS (reference), and PEDOT:Tos (control) in H_2O were determined using dynamic light scattering (DLS). Table 1 summarizes the values that indicate the nanostructured nature and polydispersity index (PDI) of the prepared biocomposites. The PEDOT:PSS reference showed a zeta potential of -77.4 mV which is in good agreement with the literature.^[53] The PPy:DNA and PEDOT:DNA particles had values -52.7 and -29.5 mV, respectively. These results indicate the negative surface charge of the particles shown illustratively in Figure 5a. The biocomposite nanoparticles display a negative zeta potential as a result of the ionized phosphate groups present in the DNA backbone. DNA as counterion decreased the negative surface charge of the nanoparticles compared to PEDOT:PSS. A similar trend was observed with another macromolecule biopolymer cellulose utilized to template PEDOT.^[53] In Figure 5b, the statistical evaluation revealed an average particle diameter of 342 ± 27 nm for PEDOT:DNA and 390 ± 38 nm for PPy:DNA particles, which corresponds to an increase of $\approx 12\%$ in the average particle size. For PEDOT:DNA, the polydispersity index was found to be 0.297 indicating the smaller particle size and good polydispersity. PPy:DNA with a subsequent formation of some larger nanoparticles resulted in a higher PDI value.

The scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of the biocomposite thin-films were investigated to assess material properties in solid state and the results were correlated to DLS findings. In Figure 6a, the micrograph image evidences more amorphous morphology of PEDOT:DNA material with an interconnected network structure as seen with higher magnification (Figure 6c). The presence of a well-interconnected morphology in the composite film can be favorable for the charge transport mechanism resulting in better conducting channels in the system.^[10] As we previously reported, PEDOT:DNA showed lower sheet resistance compared to PPy:DNA.^[24] Figure 6b demonstrates that PPy:DNA consists of aggregates of submicron spherical particles. The uniformity in size and globular structure of the particles which can be attributed to the difference in their Z potentials which plays a critical role on electrostatic repulsion between the particles and aggregation. We assume that PPy:DNA samples formed a thicker layer during device fabrication due to interaction between the particles.

The device performance of PEDOT:DNA and PPy:DNA was examined by preparing a single-channel OECT device architecture with the same device stack which was identical to our previous works.^[24,25] The devices were characterized by their steady-state behavior, as shown in Figure 7. Similar to our previously published results, both biocomposites exhibited a *p*-type OMIEC behavior operated in depletion mode. In Figure 7a, the transfer characteristic (I_D vs. V_G) of PEDOT:DNA is shown, whereby the respective determined transconductance ($g_m = \partial I_D / \partial V_G$) values are depicted as well on the right y-axis of the graph. The maximum transconductance ($g_{m\text{max}}$) reached up to 0.15 mS with an on/off ratio of 37 for this device with the same channel geometry (length/width) and a slight decrease in the channel thickness. The results are comparable to the transconductance and on/off ratio values of 0.16 mS and ≈ 300 , respectively, obtained for the same material in our previous work.^[24] We assume that the slight

Table 1. Zeta potential (ζ), Zeta average particle diameter (D_h) and polydispersity index (PDI) of the composite materials.

Material	Monomer:DNA Weight ratio	ζ / mV	D_h / nm	PDI
PEDOT:DNA	0.8:1	-29.5 ± 2.1	342 ± 27	0.297 ± 0.077
PPy:DNA	0.8:1	-52.7 ± 6.5	390 ± 38	0.402 ± 0.081
PEDOT:Tos (control)	–	21.4 ± 0.5	680 ± 31	0.309 ± 0.068
PEDOT:PSS	–	-77.4 ± 4.2	215 ± 94	0.427 ± 0.098

drop in the device performance can be associated with the reduced thickness of the channel layer.^[54] On the other hand, in Figure 7c the transfer curve as well as the respective transconductance are shown for PPy:DNA OECT devices. Thereby, a g_{\max} of 1.07 mS and an on/off ratio of 29 were recorded. With respect to our first paper, the g_{\max} was improved nearly by a factor of ≈ 18 comparing to 0.6 mS from the preliminary data.^[24] We anticipated that this improvement can be explained by the increased average film thickness to $\approx 5 \mu\text{m}$ compared to 250 nm in the previous publication. The thickness of the polymer channel plays a critical role on the device performance due to volumetric capacitance.^[54] The biocomposite PPy:DNA was prepared in 2021 and an aggregation behavior was observed in its dispersed solution due to solvent evaporation over time, which might affect the film thickness. Table 2 shows an overview of the device parameters and OECT performance obtained from the different channel materials, channel geometry and thickness. For both materials (see Figure 7b,d), the output curves show the characteristic linear increase in I_D within a V_D range from 0 to -0.3 V and reach the saturation regime. When further decreasing the voltage, the

I_D reaches a constant behavior which can be explained by the saturation of whole charges within the channel of the devices.

To eliminate the influence of channel geometry and film thickness, the normalized maximum transconductance ($g_{\max}(\text{NR})$) is also reported, and calculated using the following equation:

$$g_{\max}(\text{NR}) = g_{\max} \cdot \frac{L}{d \cdot W} \quad (1)$$

where L is the channel length, d is the film thickness, and W is the channel width.^[55] The highest $g_{\max}(\text{NR})$ values were obtained 0.18 mS cm^{-1} and 0.05 S cm^{-1} for the OECTs with PEDOT:DNA and PPy:DNA channels, respectively. The results are almost identical compared to previously fabricated OECTs with the same polymers.^[24] A small difference ($\approx 0.01 \text{ S cm}^{-1}$) in the $g_{\max}(\text{NR})$ values can be related to batch-to-batch variations during device fabrication.

$$g_{\max} = \frac{d \cdot W}{L} \mu C * |V_{\text{th}} - V_G| \quad (2)$$

Figure 5. Zeta potential distribution of A) PEDOT:DNA, PPy:DNA, and PEDOT:PSS. B) Particle size distribution (presented as diameter) and polydispersity index of the biocomposites.

Figure 6. SEM images of A) PEDOT:DNA and B) PPy:DNA recorded at 100 000 \times magnification. C) Field emission – scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM) micrograph of PEDOT:DNA at 120 000 \times magnification. (Scale bars = 500 nm).

The product of electronic mobility and volumetric charge storage capacity (μC^*) serves as a key figure of merit for the transconductance of OECTs and can be used as a benchmark to compare the performance of various OMIECs in this context.^[1] As presented in Figure S6 (Supporting Information), the threshold voltage (V_{th}) is obtained from the x-axis intercept when $-I_D^{1/2}$ is plotted as a function of gate voltage (V_G), following the method described by Li et al.^[56] The formula based on Bernhard's model is often used to evaluate μC^* : where μ is electronic carrier mobility, C^* is the volumetric capacitance, and $W d L^{-1}$ corresponds to channel dimensions.^[1] The μC^* product, extracted from steady-state OECT characteristics, provides a material-specific figure of merit that can be decoupled from device geometry and biasing conditions. It enables direct comparison between OMIECs by determining which material outperforms another. This metric

was calculated for PEDOT:DNA and PPy:DNA biocomposites as 0.29 $F V^{-1}$ and 0.11 $F V^{-1} cm^{-1} s^{-1}$, respectively. Using the same method, the μC^* value for the reference material PEDOT:PSS (Clevios PH 1000) was obtained from the transfer characteristics in Figure S7 (Supporting Information), showing good agreement with previously reported literature values.^[1] A comprehensive overview of device parameters and performance is presented in Table 2.

The obtained data is appropriate to confirm the similar device results with the existence of published data.^[24] The maximum transconductance values were an experimental validation for preserving the ion-to-electron transduction of both materials. As above-mentioned, the dispersions used for the deposition of the polymer channel were prepared in 2019/2021 and were consecutively stored in a fridge at $4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ under ambient conditions without any sonication until further usage. This proves the long-term chemical stability and applicability of the prepared dispersions for their potential use in bioelectronics. Long-term stability while preserving the initial electrical conductivity of PEDOT:PSS can be challenging after extended storage periods.^[57] Thin films fabricated from PEDOT:PSS inks without additives or post-treatment exhibit limited conductivity and stability, making them less suitable for biomedical applications.^[44] Consequently, various strategies have been proposed to improve the durability of PEDOT:PSS.^[42,44,57,58]

3. Conclusion

This study highlights the highly stable and biocompatible DNA-based mixed ionic-electronic conductors for their potential applications in future bioelectronics. In the present work, we investigated the biocompatibility and long-term chemical stability of two biocomposites PEDOT:DNA and PPy:DNA and compared these results with the reference material PEDOT:PSS (Clevios PH 1000). The fluorescent microscopy and AFM topographical images confirmed the visual determination of healthy cell morphology and cell adherence on the thin-film surfaces. Highly stable biopolymer-based conductive polymers showed no toxicity effect for NIH 3T3 fibroblast cells even after four days of cell cultivation. Additionally, the PPy:DNA and PEDOT:DNA composites were tested as channel material in OECTs to evaluate the long-term chemical stability for the shelf-life of 3 and 5 years, respectively. The results demonstrated that an efficient ion-to-electron transduction was preserved for both biocomposites after their storage at $4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ under ambient air.

We believe that our findings are promising for future research activities and will give insight into the performance of biopolymer:conductive polymer composites for implantable bioelectronics in neural recording and stimulation. As an outlook, we have to emphasize that in vivo biocompatibility and long-term stability, tests are crucial and needed before clinical applications.

4. Experimental Section

Materials: 3,4-Ethylenedioxythiophene (EDOT, 99%) was purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific. Iron (III) p-toluenesulfonate hexahydrate (FeTos) and pyrrole were procured from Sigma-Aldrich. The solution additives 4-dodecylbenzenesulfonic acid (DBSA), glycerol and (3-

Figure 7. Steady-state electrical characterization of thin-film channel PEDOT:DNA and PPy:DNA based OECTs. A) Transfer characteristics and the corresponding transconductance curve (for $V_D = -0.7$ V) and B) the corresponding output characteristics for a single-channel PEDOT:DNA OECT device ($W = 2.16$ mm, $L = 63$ μm , film thickness = 245 nm). C) Transfer characteristics and transconductance ($V_D = -0.7$ V) and D) the corresponding output characteristics for a single-channel PPy:DNA OECT device ($W = 2.17$ mm, $L = 54$ μm , film thickness = ≈ 5 μm).

glycidylxypropyl)trimethoxysilane (GOPS) were purchased from Fluka, Carl Roth, and Grolman, respectively.

Commercial Poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene):poly(styrenesulfonate) (PEDOT:PSS, Clevis PH 1000) was obtained from Heraeus Electronics GmbH (Hanau, Germany). Prior to usage, the PEDOT:PSS dispersion was filtered through a polyvinylidene fluoride filter (pore size 0.45 μm). Pyrrole was freshly distilled prior to use. All other reagents were used as received without further purification.

Purified 18 M Ω ultrapure water was obtained by the Arium Mini laboratory water system.

Synthesis of PEDOT:DNA and PPy:DNA: The synthesis of the PEDOT:DNA and PPy:DNA dispersions via chemical oxidative polymerization can be found in the previously published work.^[24] First, DNA with 0.75 wt% was dissolved in 18 m Ω water overnight at room temperature. Next, EDOT or pyrrole was added with 1:0.8 (w/w) ratio of DNA to monomer followed by 2 h of additional vigorous stirring. Subsequently, 2.5 molar equiv. of iron (III) p-toluene sulfonate hexahydrate (with respect to EDOT and pyrrole) was added. For PEDOT:DNA, the dispersion was heated to 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for several hours until the solution color changed to dark blue. The facile synthesis of Polypyrrole:DNA was carried out at room temperature

Table 2. A summary of the key device parameters and performance metrics from Figure 7 and Figure S7 (Supporting Information) and previously reported data.^[24]

Material	d / μm	W / μm	L / μm	g_{max} / mS	g_{max} [NR] / S cm^{-1}	V_G / V	$\mu\text{C}^{\circ} / \text{F V}^{-1}$ $\text{cm}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$	Refs.
PEDOT:DNA	0.26	2000	60	0.16	0.19	0.00	–	Tekoglu et al. ^[24]
PEDOT:DNA	0.25	2156	63	0.15	0.18	-0.34	0.29	This work [*]
PPy:DNA	0.25	2000	60	0.06	0.07	0.00	–	Tekoglu et al. ^[24]
PPy:DNA	≈ 5 (rough)	2165	54	1.07	0.05	0.22	0.11	This work [*]
PEDOT:PSS (PH 1000)	0.59	2140	74	39.2	23.2	0.23	63.2	This work [*]

d : film thickness, W : channel width, L : channel length, g_{max} : max. transconductance, g_{max} (NR): normalized max. transconductance.

within 30 min. After completion of the oxidative chemical polymerization, the solutions were diluted with 18 mΩ water and centrifuged at a speed of 6000 rpm for 5 min. This process was repeated four times and the dispersion was sonicated for 1 h followed by a final consecutive centrifugation and re-dispersing step. Next, the dispersion was dialyzed for 24 h by changing the water periodically. The molecular weight cut-off (MWCO) of the dialysis membrane was 12–14 kDa. Finally, the dispersions were stored in the fridge at $4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ with a relative humidity (RH) level of $\approx 60\%$ for stability tests. RH was monitored with a humidity instrument (hygrometer) in the fridge.

PEDOT:tosylate (PEDOT:Tos) as the control sample was synthesized by following the same procedure including the identical amount of EDOT and FeTos oxidant (no DNA was added this time).

Raman spectrum was recorded using a Bruker MultiRAM FT-Raman spectrometer with the excitation wavelength of 1064 nm in combination with a liquid nitrogen-cooled Ge detector. The spectrum was recorded by averaging over 10 000 scans. For the sample preparation, the aluminum foil stripe was cleaned with acetone and 18 mΩ water in an ultrasonic bath for 15 min each and dried with an N_2 spray gun. A double-sided Kapton tape was used to stick the aluminum foil on a glass slide. The dispersions of PEDOT:DNA were drop-cast onto the substrates and dried at room temperature under ambient air.

The Raman frequencies (PEDOT:DNA): 437 cm^{-1} (C–O–C deformation), 701 cm^{-1} (symmetric C–S–C deformation), 850 cm^{-1} (antisymmetrical phosphodiester (O–P–O) stretching of DNA), 988 cm^{-1} (oxyethylene ring deformation), 1095 cm^{-1} (symmetrical stretching vibration of the nucleic acid anionic phosphodiester (PO_2^-)), 1257 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}_\alpha\text{--C}_\alpha$ inter-ring stretching), 1367 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}_\beta\text{--C}_\beta$ stretching), 1417 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}_\alpha\text{--C}_\beta$ symmetrical stretching).

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were performed on a Theta Probe XPS-system (ThermoFisher, GBR), which features a monochromated Al-K α X-ray source with an energy of 1486.6 eV. The spot size on the sample surface was 400 μm in diameter. The hemispherical analyzer was set to a pass energy of 20 eV for the recorded high-resolution (HR) scans at an energy step size of 0.05 eV. The data acquisition and evaluation, as well as the control of the device, are performed via a software package (Avantage) provided by the system manufacturer. For the XPS characterization, the original stock dispersions (PEDOT:DNA and PPy:DNA) were used without further additives, whereby the dispersions were drop-cast on glass.

Zeta potential and particle size measurements were conducted using a Malvern Zetasizer Nano ZSP (Malvern Instruments Ltd., Worcestershire, UK). The dynamic light scattering (DLS) method and electrophoretic light scattering (ELS) method were utilized for determining both particle size distribution and zeta potential. The DLS measurements via intensity were performed at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, placing 1.1 mL of the sample into a disposable cuvette (DTS0012) for the particle size, and 1 mL of the sample into folded capillary cells (DTS1070) for the zeta potential determination. To prepare the sample dispersions, 10 μL of the original stock dispersion was diluted with 2 mL of mΩ water and then sonicated for 10 min using an ultrasonic processor set to 60 W with a 0.6-second pulse. Afterward, the sample dispersions were further diluted transferring 1 mL of the prepared sample into 2 mL of mΩ water. This final sample was sonicated again under the same conditions and then, six measurements were recorded for each type of measurement. The reference PEDOT:PSS dispersions were filtered through a 0.45 μm PTFE syringe filter after the dilution and sonication steps.

For the statistical evaluation of the particle size distribution, 11 and 5 measurements were considered for the biocomposites and the control samples, respectively. The zeta potential results were evaluated through 12 and 6 measurements for the biocomposites and the reference materials, respectively. Higher particle size values (above 1000 nm) were dismissed due to possible aggregation effects leading to miscalculations. The zeta potential of 0.59 mV is recorded for the dispersant, mΩ water as control.

Scanning electron microscopy analyses were conducted using the Thermo Scientific Scios 2 DualBeam instrument with an accelerating voltage of 5 kV. The composite dispersions were deposited via spin-coating on clean ITO-coated glass substrates for the SEM measurements. The micrographs were taken at 100 000 \times magnification.

Additionally, field emission – scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM) image of PEDOT:DNA (120 000 \times magnification, in Figure 6c) was recorded using a FEI FEG-Quanta 450 instrument (Field Electron and Ion Company, Hillsboro, OR, USA) at the University of Pisa (CISUP). Prior to the analysis, the sample was sputtered with platinum to improve the image quality.

In Vitro Biocompatibility Analysis—Thin-Film Preparation: For the biocompatibility of the materials, a mixture of 94.5% (v/v) dispersion (PEDOT:DNA, PPy:DNA or PDOT:PSS), 0.5% (v/v) DBSA, and 5% (v/v) glycerol was prepared, whereby subsequently 1% (v/v) GOPS was added for adherence on the glass substrates. The glass slides ($1 \times 1\text{ cm}$) were cleaned in an ultrasonic bath with a 2% (v/v) aqueous solution of Hellmanex III, deionized water, acetone, and isopropanol at 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 20 min each. Before further usage, the substrates were blow-dried with N_2 gas and oxygen plasma treated at 100 W for 5 min in a Plasma Etch PE-24 plasma cleaner. The respective material dispersions were deposited via spin-coating at 900 rpm for 60 s. The samples were annealed at 140 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1 h for cross-linking GOPS.

Cell Culture: The murine cell line NIH 3T3 purchased from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC, Manassas, VA, USA) was used for cytotoxicity testing. Cells were cultivated in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM) purchased from Life Technologies, Carlsbad, CA, USA. The culture medium contained (final concentrations in medium): 10% fetal calf serum (FCS), L-Glutamine (2 mM), and PenStrep (5 U penicillin, 50 μg streptomycin/mL). Cells were incubated at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 5% CO_2 atmosphere.

Optical Fluorescence Microscopy: Commercial plastic, microscopic glass slides (squares $1 \times 1\text{ cm}$) both as controls and samples PEDOT:DNA, PPy:DNA and PEDOT:PSS deposited on these glass substrates were incubated in the presence of NIH 3T3 (ATCC – Manassas, VA, USA) cells in 24-well plate at a density of 10,000 cells/well.

After 24, 48, and 96 h of incubation of cells on samples or controls, cells were imaged by using optical fluorescent microscopy (microscope Olympus IX 70). Before observation under the microscope, the medium was aspirated, and replaced with fresh medium containing fluorescent dyes Propidium Iodide (PI) and Calcein-AM at the final concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and 50 μM , respectively, diluted in DMSO. After 30 min incubation in the dark, the medium was replaced with PBS buffer, and cells were depicted in bright field and fluorescence mode.

Atomic Force Microscopy—Cell study: Cells after 24 h of incubation on tested samples and controls were fixed via the following procedure. The culture medium was removed and the cells were gently washed with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS). Subsequently, 1 ml of 4% paraformaldehyde solution in PBS was added to the cells for fixation. The cells were left in the refrigerator for 10 min for fixation, after which the fixing agent was aspirated followed by washing with phosphate buffer and ultrapure water. The cell sample was let to dry before measurement and put on the AFM holder and measured directly.

Combined system NTEGRA Spectra (NT-MDT, Russia) was utilized to acquire sample topography (software Nova Px. 3.4.0 rev. 19040). The surface morphology was obtained by means of semi-contact mode (height) with an ACTA-SS (AppNano, USA) cantilever having a force constant of 13–77 N m^{-1} and resonant frequency of 200–400 kHz. The scanning rate was 0.5 Hz. During the measurement the humidity was in the range of 45–55% and the temperature was RT. The height profile and surface roughness (RMS) were calculated using Gwyddion 2.5.1 software.

Cell Viability: Cell viability was assessed using a LIVE/DEAD Viability/Cytotoxicity Kit (Invitrogen) and a BD FACSVerser flow cytometer (BD Biosciences, San Jose, CA, USA). The tested samples as well as control glass samples, were washed gently with 70% ethanol and put carefully on the 24-well plate. After that, NIH 3T3 cells were seeded at a density of 50 000 cells/well. Empty wells with the same treatment were included as controls too. Heat-treated cells were incubated at 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 30 min before measurements were used as a positive control. After incubation for 24, 48, and 96 h, the supernatant containing detached cells was collected, and cells were washed with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS; 0.1 M, pH 7.4) and detached using 0.25% trypsin-EDTA solution (Gibco) for 5 min. Cells were collected in a cell culture medium and added to the supernatant. PBS

from the washing step was also collected and added to the supernatant. Collected cells were incubated with PI ($10 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) and Calcein-AM (in DMSO) for 30 min in the dark. Finally, the fluorescence signal was measured on a flow cytometer using the first two scatters (Forward scatter channel vs. Side scatter channel) and two fluorescence channels (red FL 2: ex. 488/em. 700 nm and green FL 3: ex. 488/em. 527 nm). The red PI signal marked dead cells that lost membrane integrity, whereas the green signal indicated live cells with active intracellular esterases that could catalyze the non-fluorescent Calcein-AM to highly green fluorescent Calcein. Three independent experiments were performed and mean and standard deviation \pm (SD) were calculated.

OECT Device Fabrication and Characterization: The source-drain electrode pattern was prepared by fixing the cleaned glass substrates in a shadow mask. A 10 nm of chromium (Cr) and a 100 nm of gold (Au) were sequentially evaporated via thermal vacuum deposition method at a pressure of $1\text{--}5 \times 10^{-7}$ mbar to form the single channel source-drain pairs (channel length: $L = 60 \mu\text{m}$, channel width $W = 2 \text{mm}$). Next, the channel was prepared by depositing a thin-film of the respective sample dispersions (PEDOT:DNA, PPy:DNA and PEDOT:PSS) with the above-mentioned additives via spin-coating using 900 rpm for 40 s, followed by 1200 rpm for 10 s. The area around the channel and the contacts were carefully wiped by using water-wetted cotton swabs before annealing the substrates at 140°C for 1 h. In order to increase the film thickness, the spin-coating procedure was repeated whereby additionally a short annealing step of 2 min at 140°C was employed instead of the final annealing step at 140°C for 1 h.

To complete the devices a laser-cut polymer well of 3M VHB Tape (acrylic adhesive with a conformable acrylic foam core) was fixed on the substrates to secure the aqueous electrolyte. For the device characterization, 20 μL of phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) solution (50 mM, pH 7.3) was used and a silver/silver chloride (Ag/AgCl) electrode was employed as a non-polarizable gate electrode. All steady-state current–voltage measurements were performed under ambient conditions using an Agilent model E5273A.

In order to measure the film thickness, a Bruker Dektak XT profilometer was used, whereby for the measurements a stylus force of 2 mg was applied.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

Acknowledgements

S.T. acknowledges Johannes Kepler University Linz – the Linz Institute of Technology (LIT), funded by the State of Upper Austria and the Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research for the Young Researcher Project “BIOCOM” (LIT-2022-11-YOU-221) and the European Regional Development Fund (EFRE) within the project “ENZYMIOKAT” (GZ2018-98279-2). The work was supported by European Regional Development Funds – Project “Excellence in Regenerative Medicine” (CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004562) and project “TECHSCALE” (CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004587). Prof. Sariciftci gratefully acknowledges the financial support of the Austrian Science Foundation (FWF) for receiving the Wittgenstein Prize (Z222 N19). The authors thank Prof. Alessandra Operamolla and CISUP (Center for Instrument Sharing of the University of Pisa) for the access to the FE-SEM facility.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

S.H. and K.M. contributed equally to this work. S.T. and K.P. jointly directed this work. S.H. and A.O. conducted the experiments for biocom-

patibility, cell viability, AFM imaging, and evaluated the results. K.M. carried out OECT device, Raman, and DLS experiments, and wrote the part of the manuscript. Y.S. evaluated DLS data. N.S.S. received the funding, conceived and supervised the project, designed and supervised the experimental section, and reviewed the manuscript. S.T. performed the synthesis and prepared the cytotoxicity samples, received the funding, conceived and supervised the project, designed and supervised the experimental section, analyzed the data, wrote and prepared the final draft of the manuscript with the subsequent revisions. K.P. received the funding, conceived and supervised the project, designed and supervised the experimental section, analyzed the data, wrote and reviewed the manuscript.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

biocompatibility, biocomposite, DNA, organic bioelectronics, PEDOT:PSS, polypyrrole, stability

Received: May 8, 2025

Published online:

- [1] S. Inal, G. G. Malliaras, J. Rivnay, *Nat. Commun.* **2017**, *8*, 1767.
- [2] S. Fabiano, L. Flagg, T. C. Hidalgo Castillo, S. Inal, L. G. Kaake, L. V. Kayser, S. T. Keene, S. Ludwigs, C. Muller, B. M. Savoie, B. Lüssem, J. L. Lutkenhaus, M. Matta, D. Meli, S. N. Patel, B. D. Paulsen, J. Rivnay, J. Sargailis, *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2023**, *11*, 14527.
- [3] P. Gkoupidenis, Y. Zhang, H. Kleemann, H. Ling, F. Santoro, S. Fabiano, A. Salleo, Y. van de Burgt, *Nat. Rev. Mater.* **2024**, *9*, 134.
- [4] X. Xu, Y. Zhao, Y. Liu, *Small* **2023**, *19*, 2206309.
- [5] S. Inal, J. Rivnay, A.-O. Suiiu, G. G. Malliaras, I. McCulloch, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2018**, *51*, 1368.
- [6] S. Inal, A. Hama, M. Ferro, C. Pitsalidis, J. Oziat, D. Iandolo, A.-M. Pappa, M. Hadida, M. Huerta, D. Marchat, P. Mailley, R. M. Owens, *Adv. Biosys.* **2017**, *1*, 1700052.
- [7] M. Bianchi, A. Salvo, M. Asplund, S. Carli, D. Lauro, *Adv. Sci.* **2022**, *9*, 2104701.
- [8] C. Pitsalidis, A.-M. Pappa, A. J. Boys, Y. Fu, C.-M. Moysidou, D. van Niekerk, J. Saez, A. Savva, D. Iandolo, R. M. Owens, *Chem. Rev.* **2022**, *122*, 4700.
- [9] G. M. Matrone, U. Bruno, C. Forró, C. Lubrano, S. Cinti, Y. van de Burgt, F. Santoro, *Adv. Mater. Technol.* **2023**, *8*, 2201911.
- [10] M. N. Gueye, A. Carella, J. Faure-Vincent, R. Demadrille, J.-P. Simonato, *Prog. Mater. Sci.* **2020**, *108*, 100616.
- [11] J. Rivnay, H. Wang, L. Fenno, K. Deisseroth, G. G. Malliaras, *Sci. Adv.* **2017**, *3*, 1601649.
- [12] R. M. Miriani, M. R. Abidian, D. R. Kipke, presented at Ann. Int. Conf. Vancouver, BC, Canada, August **2008**.
- [13] D. Minudri, D. Mantione, A. Dominguez-Alfaro, S. Moya, E. Maza, C. Bellacanzone, M. R. Antognazza, D. Mecerreyes, *Adv. Elect. Mater.* **2020**, *6*, 2000510.
- [14] E. Šafaříková, L. Švihálková Šindlerová, S. Střiteský, L. Kubala, M. Vala, M. Weiter, J. Vítěček, *Sens. Actuators, B* **2018**, *260*, 418.
- [15] A. R. Spencer, A. Primbetova, A. N. Koppes, R. A. Koppes, H. Fenniri, N. Annabi, *ACS Biomater. Sci. Eng.* **2018**, *4*, 1558.
- [16] Š. Tumová, R. Malečková, L. Kubáč, J. Akrman, V. Enev, L. Kalina, E. Vojtková, M. Pešková, J. Vítěček, M. Vala, M. Weiter, *Polymer J.* **2023**, *55*, 983.

- [17] S.-M. Kim, C.-H. Kim, Y. Kim, N. Kim, W.-J. Lee, E.-H. Lee, D. Kim, S. Park, K. Lee, J. Rivnay, M.-H. Yoon, *Nat. Commun.* **2018**, *9*, 3558.
- [18] G. Dijk, A. L. Rutz, G. G. Malliaras, *Adv. Mater. Technol.* **2020**, *5*, 1900662.
- [19] Y. Huang, L. Tang, Y. Jiang, *CCS Chem.* **2024**, *6*, 1844.
- [20] J. Tropp, C. P. Collins, X. Xie, R. E. Daso, A. S. Mehta, S. P. Patel, M. M. Reddy, S. E. Levin, C. Sun, J. Rivnay, *Adv. Mater.* **2024**, *36*, 2306691.
- [21] D. Mantione, I. Del Agua, A. Sanchez-Sanchez, D. Mecerreyes, *Polymers* **2017**, *9*, 354.
- [22] Y. Lee, H. Zhang, H.-Y. Yu, K. C. Tam, *Carbohydr. Polym.* **2022**, *289*, 119419.
- [23] I. A. Anisimov, R. W. Evitts, D. E. Cree, L. D. Wilson, *ACS Appl. Polym. Mater.* **2022**, *4*, 7204.
- [24] S. Tekoglu, D. Wielend, M. C. Scharber, N. S. Sariciftci, C. Yumusak, *Adv. Mater. Technol.* **2020**, *5*, 1900699.
- [25] K. Matura, R. D'Orsi, L. Spagnuolo, F. Mayr, M. Cobet, C. Putz, A. Operamolla, S. Tekoglu, *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2024**, *12*, 16701.
- [26] S. Carli, M. Bianchi, D. Lauro, P. M., T. M., L. A., S. M., A. de, M. Murgia, L. Fadiga, F. Biscarini, *Front Mater.* **2022**, *9*, 1063763.
- [27] C. Chen, Y. Yu, K. Li, M. Zhao, L. Liu, J. Yang, J. Liu, D. Sun, *Cellulose* **2015**, *22*, 3929.
- [28] M. Asplund, E. Thaning, J. Lundberg, A. C. Sandberg-Nordqvist, B. Kostyszyn, O. Inganäs, H. Holst, *Biomed. Mater.* **2009**, *4*, 045009.
- [29] Y. Ner, M. A. Invernale, J. G. Grote, J. A. Stuart, G. A. Sotzing, *Synth. Met.* **2010**, *160*, 351.
- [30] B. Singh, N. S. Sariciftci, J. G. Grote, F. K. Hopkins, *J. Appl. Phys.* **2006**, *100*, 024514.
- [31] C. Yumusak, T. B. Singh, N. S. Sariciftci, J. G. Grote, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2009**, *95*, 263304.
- [32] S. Tekoglu, M. Held, M. Bender, G. N. Yeo, A. Kretzschmar, M. Hamburger, J. Freudenberger, S. Beck, U. H. F. Bunz, G. Hernandez-Sosa, *Adv. Sustainable Syst.* **2021**, *5*, 2000203.
- [33] F. Ouchen, P. P. Yaney, C. M. Bartsch, E. M. Heckman, J. G. Grote, in *Nanobiosystems: Processing, Characterization, and Applications III* (Eds. N. Kobayashi, F. Ouchen, I. Rau), SPIE, San Diego, California, **2010**, 77650A.
- [34] A. Håkansson, S. Han, S. Wang, J. Lu, S. Braun, M. Fahlman, M. Berggren, X. Crispin, S. Fabiano, *J. Polym. Sci. B Polym. Phys.* **2017**, *55*, 814.
- [35] S. Zhang, E. Hubis, C. Girard, P. Kumar, J. DeFranco, F. Cicoira, *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2016**, *4*, 1382.
- [36] V. V. Tuchin, A. Tárnok, V. P. Zharov, *Cytometry Pt A* **2011**, *79A*, 737.
- [37] A. C. Bakke, *Lab. Med.* **2001**, *32*, 207.
- [38] S. Hradilova, T. Zavadna, J. Belza, M. Irimia-Vladu, N. S. Sariciftci, C. Yumusak, K. Polakova, *Microchem. J.* **2024**, *202*, 110740.
- [39] ISO 10993-5:2009 (2009) Biological Evaluation of Medical Devices. Part 5: Tests for In Vitro Cytotoxicity, Geneva, Switzerland, <https://www.iso.org/standard/36406.html>.
- [40] C. Chen, T. Zhang, Q. Zhang, Z. Feng, C. Zhu, Y. Yu, K. Li, M. Zhao, J. Yang, J. Liu, D. Sun, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2015**, *7*, 28244.
- [41] A. Dominguez-Alfaro, N. Casado, M. Fernandez, A. Garcia-Esnaola, J. Calvo, D. Mantione, M. R. Calvo, A. L. Cortajarena, *Small* **2024**, *20*, 2307536.
- [42] D. Won, J. Kim, J. Choi, H. Kim, S. Han, I. Ha, J. Bang, K. K. Kim, Y. Lee, T.-S. Kim, J.-H. Park, C.-Y. Kim, S. H. Ko, *Sci. Adv.* **2022**, *8*, abo3209.
- [43] B. Oh, S. Baek, K. S. Nam, C. Sung, C. Yang, Y.-S. Lim, M. S. Ju, S. Kim, T.-S. Kim, S.-M. Park, S. Park, S. Park, *Nat. Commun.* **2024**, *15*, 5839.
- [44] S. Střiteský, A. Marková, J. Víteček, E. Šafaříková, M. Hrabal, L. Kubáč, L. Kubala, M. Weiter, M. Vala, *J. Biomed. Mater. Res., Part A* **2018**, *106*, 1121.
- [45] M. Ghasemi, T. Turnbull, S. Sebastian, I. Kempson, *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* **2021**, *22*, 12827.
- [46] C. J. Whitfield, M. Zhang, P. Winterwerber, Y. Wu, D. Y. W. Ng, T. Weil, *Chem. Rev.* **2021**, *121*, 11030.
- [47] R. Wu, W. Li, P. Yang, N. Shen, A. Yang, X. Liu, Y. Ju, L. Lei, B. Fang, *J. Nanobiotechnol.* **2024**, *22*, 518.
- [48] T. A. Skotheim, *Handbook of Conducting Polymers*, Marcel Dekker Inc, New York **1986**.
- [49] N. K., C. S. Rout, *RSC Adv.* **2021**, *11*, 5659.
- [50] Z. Zhang, M. Rouabhia, S. Moulton, *Conductive Polymers: Electrical Interactions in Cell Biology and Medicine*, CRC Press Taylor & Francis Group, Boca Raton FL **2017**.
- [51] K. Vega-Figueroa, J. Santillán, V. Ortiz-Gómez, E. O. Ortiz-Quiles, B. A. Quiñones-Colón, D. A. Castilla-Casadiegos, J. Almodóvar, M. J. Bayro, J. A. Rodríguez-Martínez, E. Nicolau, *ACS Omega* **2018**, *3*, 1437.
- [52] X. Li, M. Wan, X. Li, G. Zhao, *Polymer* **2009**, *50*, 4529.
- [53] M. Horikawa, T. Fujiki, T. Shirotsaki, N. Ryu, H. Sakurai, S. Nagaoka, H. Ihara, *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2015**, *3*, 8881.
- [54] J. Rivnay, P. Leleux, M. Ferro, M. Sessolo, A. Williamson, D. A. Koutsouras, D. Khodagholy, M. Ramuz, X. Strakosas, R. M. Owens, C. Benar, J.-M. Badier, C. Bernard, G. G. Malliaras, *Sci. Adv.* **2015**, *1*, 1400251.
- [55] D. Ohayon, V. Druet, S. Inal, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2023**, *52*, 1001.
- [56] P. Li, J. Shi, Y. Lei, Z. Huang, T. Lei, *Nat. Commun.* **2022**, *13*, 5970.
- [57] B. Adilbekova, A. D. Scaccabarozzi, H. Faber, M. I. Nugraha, V. Bruevich, D. Kaltsas, D. R. Naphade, N. Wehbe, A.-H. Emwas, H. N. Alshareef, V. Podzorov, J. Martín, L. Tsetseris, T. D. Anthopoulos, *Adv. Mater.* **2024**, *36*, 2405094.
- [58] S. Doshi, M. O. A. Forner, P. Wang, S. E. Hadwe, A. T. Jin, G. Dijk, K. Brinson, J. Lim, A. Dominguez-Alfaro, C. Y. J. Lim, A. Salleo, D. G. Barone, G. Hong, M. L. Brongersma, N. A. Melosh, G. G. Malliaras, S. T. Keene, *Adv. Mater.* **2025**, *37*, 2415827.